

TASK FOR DEVELOPMENT OF CATERING SERVICES NETWORK IN TOURISM AND HOTELS

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Abstract: This article highlights the current tasks of the development of the network of catering services in tourism and hotels. The importance of general catering services in regions where the tourism industry is developing, modern trends in the provision of these services, meeting customer needs and improving the quality of service are analyzed. Also, the economic impact of the catering industry on the tourism sector, innovative approaches to the provision of catering services and the possibilities of using digital technologies are considered. The article also provides recommendations and strategies for the development of the sector.

Keywords: Tourism hotel, Catering services, Innovative approaches, Digital technologies, Quality of service, Customer needs Economic impact, Modern trends Strategies.

Economical and rational use of food at home is not organized in the same way as in public catering. Participation in all functions of the reproduction process of this industry shows its active influence on the social and economic life of the society. The development of a catering network requires the following tasks:

- improvement of the types of food establishments (towns) (adjusting to the mentality of the population), rationalization of their location;
- improving the quality of products, adapting them to scientifically based standards of rational consumption quality;
- adaptation of meals to the consumption complex (breakfast, lunch, dinner, wedding ceremonies, etc.);
- adapting the aesthetic and cultural aspects of the eating process to the requirements of the customers (consumers);
- industrialization of food industry, improvement of technology, introduction of new progressive methods of service;
- such as improvement of services based on the mentality of the population using foreign experiences.

As can be seen from the definition of catering establishments, they perform three main functions: organizing the production, sale and consumption of food

products by the population in specially organized places, but in addition to these functions, the functions of catering establishments include "organizing leisure and social events of the population should also be included. One of the promising directions for the development of innovative activities is the organization of catering services. This is supported by the high growth dynamics and quality changes in the development of food production markets. The main task of innovative activity is the function of change for the better. Innovative processes are taking place in all sectors of the economy, including raw materials and the hospitality industry, as one of the main segments of modern business.

The increase in the standard and quality of life of the population has slightly changed the traditional culture of raw materials. Cooking and ready-made food stores (departments) are very popular today, so large catering enterprises, including supermarkets and retail chains, are actively developing food production, opening specialized departments.

The main trends in the development of nutrition in Uzbekistan include:

- ❖ An increase in the number of whole food chain enterprises. The number of enterprises such as bars and cafes increased, especially in the public network, and kitchens in recreation centers of the specialized network (the number of enterprises increased by 3 times), while the number of canteens decreased significantly (the number of enterprises decreased by 3 times). All this leads to the fact that the turnover of catering enterprises has a stable growth pattern;

- ❖ Increasing consumer demand for the quality of services provided by catering establishments. In order to meet the ever-increasing demands of the consumer, enterprises working in the catering sector hold corporate trainings and various professional forums aimed at sharing experiences in the catering sector and finding solutions to emerging problems;

- ❖ Uneven development of the catering market. Uneven development is both qualitative and geographical in nature. The quality of services provided in the central cities of the regions is much higher than this indicator in the rest of the regions;

- ❖ Entry of new players into the catering market. The continuous development of the city of Samarkand attracts the main players in the field of catering, regionally and throughout Uzbekistan, and even at the world level.

To summarize, the subject of product and turnover of catering establishments includes several main aspects: Food menu: catering establishments offer a variety of food and drinks to their audience. This includes the development and presentation of a variety of culinary products, special menus for different

seasons and customer preferences. Product quality: It is important to ensure the quality of the products used - freshness, purity, naturalness and compliance with safety standards. Quality control of products and suppliers plays an important role in the success of the enterprise. Procurement of Products: An effective procurement system must be developed to meet the needs of the enterprise for all the necessary products and ingredients. This includes finding and selecting reliable suppliers, negotiating prices and terms of cooperation.

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